

HARMONIZATION OF THE CONDITIONS OF THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT BY MEANS OF LANDSCAPE DESIGN

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of harmonization of the urban environment by methods and means of certain aspects of landscape design. In modern conditions, park areas play an important role in solving the problems of preserving the environment in the city, creating conditions that have a beneficial effect on the psychophysical state of a person.

Key words: landscape design, green spaces, parks, psychological impact, crown, urban environment, park areas, amusement park, silhouette, form.

In modern conditions, the task of preserving and improving the environment in the city, the formation of conditions in the urban environment that have a beneficial effect on the psychophysical state of a person is very important. This task is of great importance during the period of intensive growth of cities, the development of various types of transport, and the acceleration of the rhythm of urban life. At present, the issue of psychology is also very significant, since a person most of the time is forced to be in an artificial environment, where the visual component often leaves much to be desired.

Landscape design is a real factor in maintaining a balance between the natural environment and the artificial components of the urban environment, the key to maintaining its sustainability. The design of eco-plantings is becoming an essential tool for ecological well-being. One of the main elements of landscape design, along with relief and water devices is vegetation. The role of living plants cannot be overestimated.

One of the most important environmental goals in the city is the creation of green areas (city parks, boulevards, squares). Green spaces are a system that restores the environment and ensures the comfort of living conditions for people in the city. In addition, it is green spaces that regulate the composition of the air and the degree of its pollution, the microclimatic characteristics of urban areas, and effectively combat the influence of the noise factor.

The landscape as an object of scientific research is presented in the works of several authors, such as V.V. Dokuchaev, A.L. Krasnova, G.F. Morozov and others; as an object of creative activity in the works of N.V. Kocherezhko, I.P. Lepkovich, S.A. Mishina, N.A. Nekhuzhenko, A.V. Sycheva, V.A. Nefedova and others [1] They outlined the structure, theoretical foundations and methodological features of the subject being studied.

Much attention has always been paid to urban greening in Uzbekistan. Since ancient times, "to improve the microclimate, city-wide and intra-district reservoirs-houses were arranged on the banks of which wide-crowned shady trees (elms, weeping willows, etc.) were

grown, teahouses were arranged and in turn, contributed not only to coolness, but also great expressiveness of urban ensembles" [2].

A well-formed system of green spaces in the urban environment contributes to the solution of several tasks: functional, environmental, artistic.

The positive impact of vegetation is directly related to the environmental sustainability of the urban environment: reducing noise intensity, dust concentration in the air, etc. Plants saturate the air with oxygen, affect air temperature, humidity, and reduce pollution.

The proximity of traffic flows and heavy foot traffic create problems for the development of vegetation in urban transit spaces. Therefore, the correct selection of vegetation and further competent operation play an important role.

The resistance of the selected vegetation to adverse factors of the anthropogenic environment, its ability to recover after any damage, phytoncides should be the basis for designing a system of green spaces and the reconstruction of urban spaces. [3]

From the point of view of video ecology, plants save from the dull appearance of monotonous homogeneous surfaces of concrete buildings, helping to improve the psychological state of a person. First of all, plants are the "source" of green, so useful for calming the nervous system. In addition, the presence of living green spaces softens the impact of the urban environment on humans. Plants often play the role of a background for buildings, giving the architectural environment scale.

The system of green spaces in the city consists of parks, squares, boulevards, embankments, alleys, landscaped open public spaces, etc. Pedestrian spaces provide compositional and functional interaction between architectural objects and the landscape environment and are used for recreation and communication. [4]

Park areas are one of the best means of maintaining "environmental health". Their ecological role cannot be overestimated. Park areas increase the attractiveness of urban areas. It is known that the reconstruction of green areas increases the value of the property located near (for example, near Central Park in New York) [5]. In addition, in the structure of the city, parks should be integrated into the so-called ecological framework, consisting of boulevards, squares, embankments, etc.

One of the most important objects of landscape design are parks with various functions. So, parks in the city can be multifunctional and specialized (sports, walking, exhibition, zoological, botanical, ethnographic, memorial, amusement parks, etc.). However, parks are primarily an artificial natural environment in the city, created by human hands. As a rule, people come to parks to relax and get away from the bustle of the city. The mood of the people who come depends on the message the author-designer puts in this park.

In addition, parks can also be considered as one of the options for the further development of the city, as well as an effective tool for branding the city. Park areas can generate income, serve as entertainment, attract tourists, and play a positive cultural role.

Thus, in the world practice there are many examples of successful planning of parks, which are a popular place for residents and points of attraction for tourists.

In Germany, the largest amusement park "Europe-Park" is the second most visited park in Europe after "Disneyland" in Paris.

Here are various attractions that are located in 16 thematic sections of the park, representing 13 states. On the territory of each, you can learn about local customs, get acquainted with the peculiarities of the national costume and try traditional cuisine. Theatrical performances are held in the park, conferences are held, television programs are often filmed [6].

In the city of Orlando, USA, the Magical World of Harry Potter Park is located on eight hectares of land, where the magical world was reconstructed. The park contains the village of Hogsmeade, the Three Broomsticks restaurant, the Hogwarts Express steam locomotive, and a replica of the School of Witchcraft and Wizardry. All entertainment in the park relates to the plots of books and films about Harry Potter [7].

This is the Hippogriff Flight attraction, Hagrid's hut, Ollivander's shop, where you can find magic wands and various models of brooms for participating in a Quidditch tournament. Thanks to the painstaking work of the designers, the interiors of the castle were recreated with detailed accuracy. It should be noted that with the advent of this park, there was even a slight decline in attendance at Walt Disney World, the construction of which turned Orlando from an inconspicuous village into a thriving tourist center.

Efteling is one of the oldest theme parks in the Dutch province of North Brabant. The park stands out for its architecture, because most of the park's buildings were created in accordance with famous Dutch fairy tales and therefore are especially loved by children and their parents. A large number of attractions have been built on the territory of Efteling. The park is one of the 25 most visited theme parks in the world [6].

The largest amusement park Everland in South Korea includes 5 large areas that offer a variety of entertainment, as well as colorful and enchanting events all year round: Tulip Festival, Rose Festival, Illumination Festival, etc. Along with the rides, Everland also has the Zootopia animal zone, which has about 2,000 animals that can be observed from a close distance. Since 2013, Zootopia has been running an exciting Lost Valley safari tour, which involves seeing animals on small sightseeing buses. During such a trip, guests of the park can admire about 150 animals [8].

Drawing.1 Everland Park, South Korea

Park areas play an important role in both large and small cities. These examples show that the creation of a popular specialized park with an interesting theme can become the basis of a marketing strategy, increase tourist flow, attract investors, and improve the economy of a settlement. This will support its brand and have a great impact on the image of the city and improve the quality of life of citizens.

However, speaking about the ecological role of park areas for citizens, the selection of plants is of great importance when designing parks. Of course, there are several criteria here. When selecting an assortment of plants for planting in a park, landscape designers must consider the functional, ecological and decorative qualities of plants. Thus, coniferous species enrich the air with oxygen, ionize it, and act as biological filters [9]. In addition, conifers in spring and autumn create a contrast with deciduous trees, and in summer they serve as an excellent backdrop for them. Coniferous trees can divide spaces into certain zones, serve as a hedge, a "screen" to cover any part of the territory.

Of great importance is the psychological impact of the color and shape of the crown of deciduous trees [10]. In the spring, during the period of active flowering of trees, the urban environment is transformed. So, admiring the beauty of cherry blossoms in Japan is one of the highest aesthetic pleasures. It is known that vivid emotions of joy are caused in people by the variety of colors of the foliage of trees, observed during the period of "golden autumn". The perception of color largely depends on the level of natural light.

Thus, special attention should be paid to the color of vegetation. It actively affects the human senses and their psychophysiological state. The color scheme of plant groups, water devices, various compositions of stones is perceived not only by sight, but by the whole organism (including hearing, touch, smell, etc.). The emotional reaction to color is due to the appearance of certain associations. The emotional impact of color determines the color ratio of the compositions. They are built according to the rules of color harmony as contrasting or nuanced. The use of color in landscape compositions mainly comes down to the juxtaposition of warm and cold, light and dark, bright and restrained tones.

Regardless of age, the human eye primarily perceives light, then follows the perception of color and then the shape of tree crowns and the nature of the structure of branches, etc. Without the necessary illumination, a person cannot perceive the objective world. Consequently, light and the shadows generated by it are of paramount importance in the perception of landscape compositions.

All trees have their own natural crown shape. However, the silhouette is formed not only under the influence of natural data, but also with the help of curly cutting of trees - topiary art, known since ancient times. The shape of the tree crown is especially clearly visible in tapeworms and in avenue plantings.

According to studies, trees with classic landscape silhouettes, with a natural, spreading, asymmetric and tiered crown, create the so-called "optimistic", positive, "sunny" atmosphere. These trees include oak, ash, acacia, field maple. Another inspiring effect was found in trees with a spreading crown shape. The atmosphere of sophistication, rigor and solemnity is created by plants with a columnar or pyramidal crown shape (such as junipers, thuja, cypress). Such plants set the rhythm, the clarity of the composition, the severity, the effect of the dominant. At the same time, it is believed that the conical shape of the crown is dynamic, it encourages a person to take initiative and creativity. The columnar shape is more balanced, evokes more elevated feelings in people.

The spherical geometric shape creates a feeling of security, peace and tranquility, maintains peace of mind. Plants with a round shape of the crown have a positive effect on humans. Woody with a spherical or oval crown contributes to the achievement of internal harmony (horse chestnut, linden). The umbrella shape of the tree crown has a calming effect

(Albizia), and the weeping forms of trees create a lyrical, nostalgic atmosphere (Babylonian willow, etc.).

Not only natural, but also artificially formed crowns quite strongly influence the human psyche. A great effect, especially on children, is produced by various shrubs cut in the form of zoomorphic and biomorphic motifs (birds, animals, plants). Artistic cutting of trees and shrubs can be used as a calming factor.

When designing parks for various purposes (depending on specialization), one should consider the psychological impact that plants planted in a particular space have.

Thus, a competent selection of plants creates conditions for a favorable ecological balance, as well as psychological balance in people. A characteristic feature of the work of a landscape designer is the inseparable connection between the creative design process and artistic and research activities in order to achieve harmony in the object-spatial environment and human life.

References:

- 1.Nefedov. V. A. Ландшафтный дизайн и устойчивость среды. Landscape design and environment sustainability. – СПб.: Полиграфист, 2002
- 2.Kadirova T. F. Пути архитектурного возрождения Узбекистана за XX - начала XX вв. ТАСИ, Т.2007
- 3.Vetlugina A. V., Dobronravova E. A., Fomenko N. N. Environmental trends in modern architectural design //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 487-491.
- 4.Norbaeva M., & Vetlugina, A.V. (2022). Ecological Design of the Urban Environment. Journal of Architectural Design, 10, 6–8.
<https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/jad/article/view/2195>
- 5.World Urban Parks: как парки меняют города и делают людей равными.
<https://news.rambler.ru/other/43037380-world-urban-parks-kak-parki-menyayut-goroda-i-delayut-lyudey-ravnymi/>
- 6.<https://realty.rbc.ru/news/5c59ce419a7947032e86c8d6>
- 7.www.universalorlando.com/harrypotter.
- 8.<http://www.everland.com/web/multi/english/everland/main.html>
- 9.Principles Ecological Landscape Design, Travis Beck. Printed using Franklin Gothic Condensed. ISBN 978-1-59726-701-4, 2013.
- 10.Yalandina N/ M. Буферные зеленые зоны в архитектурной среде.
http://book.uraic.ru/project/conf/txt/005/archvuz18_pril/5/template_article-ar=K01-20-k05.htm